

Extraction chromatographic method of indium(III) with *n*-capric acid

Bhabatosh Mandal and U. S. Roy*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati, Santiniketan-731 235, India

E-mail : root@vbharat.ernet.in Fax : 91-03463-52-672

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A selective method has been developed for extraction chromatographic studies of In^{III} with *n*-capric acid (liquid cation exchanger) coated on silica gel as a stationary phase. Its quantitative extraction has been achieved from acetate buffer solution in the pH range 3.75–5.5. The effects of pH, stripping agent, flow rate on extraction as well as elution have been investigated. Exchange capacity of the exchanger at different temperatures with respect to In^{III} has been determined. In^{III} has been separated from various elements in their binary and multicomponent mixtures. Sequential separation of In^{III} from the synthetic mixtures has been performed.

Separation of In^{III} through solvent extraction with high molecular mass carboxylic acid¹, extraction and separation of In^{III} with T.B.P. as an extractant using silica gel as supporting material², separator of In^{III} from other elements through extraction chromatography with Versatic-10 (C₁₀-monocarboxylic acid)³ and with S.R.S.-100 (C₁₅-monocarboxylic acid)⁴ have been reported. Extraction chromatographic studies of metal ions with commercial extractants have also been reported⁵. This paper reports systematic investigation on extraction chromatography of In^{III} and its sequential separation from Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and Tl^{III} with high molecular mass carboxylic acid, *n*-capric acid.

Results and Discussion

Chromatographic behavior of In^{III} with *n*-capric acid ensured quantitative extraction from acetate buffer at pH 3.5–5.5 and retained completely even at a flow rate of 2.5 ml min⁻¹. Common anions like NO₃⁻, halide, SO₄²⁻ and ClO₄⁻ did not interfere in the extraction.

Stripping agents : The elution behavior of In^{III} with HCl (0.001–0.005 M), H₂SO₄ (0.0015–0.01 M), HNO₃ (0.003–0.01 M), acetic acid (0.05–0.5 M) and deionised water was tested. Separations of In^{III} from most of the metal ions were achieved by using 0.01 M HNO₃ as eluent. Hence, 0.01 M HNO₃ was preferred as eluting agent.

Binary separation : The feed was prepared by mixing an aliquot of standard solution of In^{III} (3.0 mg) and one of the other metal ions to be separated in acetate buffer solution. The desired separation of In^{III} was achieved either by controlling the pH or by using specific eluents. At pH 4.5, In^{III} with any one of the metal ion such as Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ca^{II} and Cr^{III}, only In^{III} was extracted while the other metal ions passed through with the mobile phase. Extracted In^{III} was eluted with 0.01 M HNO₃ and estimated

complexometrically⁶. Binary mixture containing In^{III} with Fe^{III} or Zr^{IV} when was passed through the column at pH 2.5, In^{III} passed through with the mobile phase. Extracted Fe^{III} and Zr^{IV} were eluted with 0.5 M H₂SO₄ and 4 M HNO₃, respectively. However, In^{III} with any one of the metal ions such as Al^{III}, Ga^{III}, Tl^{III}, La^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Pb^{II}, Th^{IV} and U^{VI} when passed through the column at pH 4.5, both of them were extracted. Separation from each other was achieved by using selective eluting agents, e.g. Al^{III} with 0.002 M HNO₃, Ga^{III} with 0.01 M HNO₃, Tl^{III} with 0.5 M HNO₃, La^{III} with 0.002 M HNO₃, Ce^{IV} with 1 M H₂SO₄, Pb^{II} with 0.001 M HNO₃, Th^{IV} with 0.25 M HNO₃ and U^{VI} with 0.001 M HNO₃. In the case of separation of In^{III} from Tl^{III}, Ce^{IV} and Th^{IV}, In^{III} was eluted first with 0.01 M HNO₃, followed by the elution of rest of the metal ions with specific eluents (mentioned above). During the separation of In^{III} from Al^{III}, La^{III}, Pb^{II} and U^{VI}, these metals ions were eluted first with specific eluents (mentioned above) followed by the elution of In^{III}. In the case of Ga^{III}- In^{III} mixture, after extraction at pH 4.5, In^{III} was first eluted with 0.002 M HCl, followed by Ga^{III} with 0.01 M HNO₃. Quantitative separations were achieved in most of the cases.

Separation of In^{III} from multicomponent synthetic mixtures : In order to determine the possible analytical applications, the proposed method was applied to separate In^{III} from several synthetic mixtures containing group of metal ions, commonly associated with In^{III} in ores and alloy samples. The results are given in Table 1. Since all the mixtures contain Fe^{III}, in each case the initial extraction was done at pH 2.5 when only Fe^{III} was extracted which was eluted with 0.5 M H₂SO₄. From the effluent quantitative separation of other metal ions were achieved by using selective condition for extraction and elution.

Separation of Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III} : After the separa-

Table 1. Separation of In^{III} from synthetic multicomponent mixtureIn^{III} taken = 3.00 mg, Column = 0.8 × 8 cm Flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹, pH = 4.50, 2.50%, eluent used 0.01 M HNO₃, 0.002 M HCl**

Sl no	Cation	Wt. of metal ion (mg)		Recovery %	Relative error %	Eluent used	Eluent volume ml
		Added	Recovered				
1	*Fe ^{III}	1.78	1.79	100.56	+0.56	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	40
	Al ^{III}	2.50	2.48	99.20	-0.80	0.002 M HNO ₃	80
	In ^{III}	3.00	2.98	99.66	-0.33	0.01 M HNO ₃	50
	Tl ^{III}	1.49	1.52	103.00	+2.01	0.5 M HNO ₃	50
2	*Fe ^{III}	1.73	1.80	101.12	+1.12	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	40
	Cr ^{III}	2.45	2.44	99.59	-0.41	-	50
	Al ^{III}	2.50	2.48	99.20	-0.82	0.002 M HNO ₃	80
	In ^{III}	3.00	3.01	100.33	+0.33	0.01 M HNO ₃	50
3	*Fe ^{III}	1.78	1.79	100.56	+0.56	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	40
	Cr ^{III}	2.45	2.43	99.12	-0.82	-	50
	In ^{III}	3.00	3.02	100.67	+0.67	0.01 M HNO ₃	50
	Tl ^{III}	1.49	1.48	99.33	-0.67	0.5 M HNO ₃	50
4	*Fe ^{III}	1.78	1.80	101.12	+1.12	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	40
	La ^{III}	6.66	6.68	100.30	+0.30	0.002 M HNO ₃	40
	In ^{III}	3.00	2.97	99.00	-1.00	0.01 M HNO ₃	50
	Tl ^{III}	1.40	1.48	99.33	-0.67	0.5 M HNO ₃	50
5	*Fe ^{III}	1.78	1.80	101.12	+1.12	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	40
	In ^{III}	3.00	3.01	100.33	+0.33	0.002 M HCl	50
	U ^{VI}	3.00	2.99	99.67	-0.33	0.001 M HNO ₃	50
	Th ^{IV}	3.25	3.23	99.38	-0.62	0.25 N HNO ₃	50
6	Al ^{III}	2.50	2.52	100.80	+0.80	0.005 N H ₂ SO ₄	40
	Ga ^{III}	2.00	1.98	99.00	-1.00	0.25 M HCl	30
	**In ^{III}	3.00	3.02	100.67	+0.67	0.01 N HNO ₃	50
	**Tl ^{III}	1.49	1.48	99.33	-0.67	0.5 M HNO ₃	50

tion of Fe^{III} from the mixture containing Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III}, the effluent was passed through the column at pH 4.5 where Al^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III} were quantitatively extracted. Al^{III} was eluted first with 0.002 M HNO₃, In^{III} with 0.01 M HNO₃ and finally Tl^{III} was eluted with 0.5 M HNO₃.

Separation of Fe^{III}, Cr^{III}, Al^{III} and In^{III}: Fe^{III} was separated first from the mixture. Rest of the metal ions Cr^{III}, Al^{III} and In^{III} present in the mixture was passed through the column at pH 4.5 when except Cr^{III}, both Al^{III} and In^{III} were extracted. Al^{III} was eluted with 0.002 M HNO₃ followed by In^{III} with 0.01 M HNO₃.

Separation of Fe^{III}, Cr^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III}: From the mixture, Fe^{III} was selectively separated first. The effluent containing rest of the metal ions was passed through the column at pH 4.5, when except Cr^{III}, both In^{III} and Tl^{III} were extracted. Quantitative separation was achieved by eluting first In^{III} with 0.01 M HNO₃, followed by Tl^{III} with 0.5 M HNO₃.

Separation of Fe^{III}, In^{III}, U^{VI} and Th^{IV}: On passing the

effluent at pH 4.5 after the separation of Fe^{III}, rest of the metal ions were extracted in the column. In^{III} was eluted first with 0.002 M HCl, U^{VI} with 0.001 M HNO₃, followed by Th^{IV} with 0.25 M HNO₃.

Separation of Fe^{III}, La^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III}: From the mixture, Fe^{III} was selectively separated first. The effluent containing La^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III} was passed at pH 4.5 when La^{III} was eluted first with 0.002 M HNO₃, then In^{III} eluted with 0.01 M HNO₃, followed by Tl^{III} with 0.5 M HNO₃.

Sequential separation of Al^{III}, Ga^{III}, In^{III} and Tl^{III} from each other: These metal ions were extracted from the synthetic mixture when passed through the column at pH 4.5. In^{III} and Tl^{III} were eluted first with 0.002 M HCl followed by the elution of Al^{III} with 0.005 M H₂SO₄ and Ga^{III} with 0.25 M HCl. The effluent containing In^{III} and Tl^{III} was passed again through the column at pH 4.5 when both of them were extracted. In^{III} and Tl^{III} were separated from each other by eluting them with 0.01 M HNO₃ and 0.5 M HNO₃, respectively.

Experimental

An Elico LI-120 pH meter, a thermostat and chromatographic column (0.8 × 8 cm) were used. *n*-Capric acid (Shell Chemical) was used. Stock solution of In^{III} (3.0 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from In(NO₃) (Glaxo) and standardised complexometrically with EDTA⁶.

The ion-exchanger was prepared according to the usual method⁷. *n*-Capric acid (0.9 ml) coated silica gel (1 g) in distilled water was prepared by centrifugation at 1500 rpm and was taken in a column to achieve a bed height of 8 cm. The column was washed with 4 M HCl. Each exchanger bed could be used at least 25 cycles with its full exchange capacity. The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger, H⁺-form was determined at different temperatures by measuring the meq. of sodium ion absorbed by 1 g of the dry exchanger⁴. The capacity was found to be 1.84–1.96 meq. of H⁺/g in the temperature range 25–60°.

General extraction procedure : The desired pH of the exchanger bed (0.8 × 8 cm) containing *n*-capric acid coated

silica gel was adjusted with acetate buffer solution. An aliquot of solution containing 3 mg of In^{III} in 10 ml acetate buffer at pH 4.5 was passed through the column with a flow rate of 1 ml min⁻¹. The extracted In^{III} was eluted with 0.01 M HNO₃ and estimated complexometrically⁶.

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